

Mesoporous Bioactive Glass – Part 1: Processing and Application

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ABSTRACT

According to the IUPAC definition, porous materials are divided into three classes: microporous (<2 nm), mesoporous (2–50 nm) and macroporous (>50 nm) [1]. Ordered mesoporous silica was first discovered in 1992 [2], and proposed as a drug delivery system in 2001 [3]. Since then silica-based glass microspheres, such as MCM-41, SBA-15 or MCM-48 type ordered mesoporous glass materials have been considered as an ideal material for incorporation of drugs, genes and other therapeutic agent carriers and control release systems. Mesoporous bioactive glasses can be prepared by sol-gel method, which is a wet-chemistry process for producing materials from building blocks such as the silicate tetrahedra, structural directive agents and metallic ions. This process mainly involves hydrolysis and condensation of precursors, drying, and stabilization. By controlling the processing parameters, the properties of the reaction product, such as its morphology and chemical and phase composition can be readily controlled. For the sol-gel synthesis of bioactive glasses, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) is the most widely used silicate precursor, while water and/or ethanol are used as solvents. The sol-gel process can take place under acidic or basic conditions, affecting the properties of the resulting materials: a simple changing of the pH of the solvent yields bioactive glasses with different morphology. In a typical sol-gel process used for preparation of bioactive glass nanoparticles, TEOS firstly undergoes hydrolysis and condensation in the presence of catalysts and structural directive agent to form SiO₂ nanoparticles. Metal ion precursors can be added during the hydrolysis and condensation of TEOS or after the formation of SiO₂ nanoparticles. The resulting nanoparticles are then dried and calcined.

In this preliminary study microemulsion sol-gel method was used for the preparation of mesoporous bioactive glass particles with spherical shape, monodispersed size and low degree of agglomeration. Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable, isotropic liquid mixtures of oil phase, aqueous phase and surfactants. In contrast to the formation of conventional emulsions usually requiring shear effects, microemulsions can form by simply mixing the components, which are then stabilized by the presence of surfactants [4], [5]. The schematic of the process of preparation of mesoporous glass nanoparticles via microemulsion method is shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 Preparation of Mesoporous Bioactive Glass Nanoparticles

In the present work, 2.8 g cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB soft template) was dissolved in 132 ml of water under continuous stirring for 15 min. Then, 40 ml of ethyl acetate was poured into the

above solution. Aqueous solution of ammonium hydroxide (28%) and 14.4 ml of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) were then added into the solution under continuous stirring. Finally, 10.15 g of calcium nitrate tetrahydrate was added, followed by magnetic stirring for 30 min. The solution was allowed to react for 4 h. After that, the suspension was filtrated and washed with deionized water and ethanol to remove unreacted precursors and remaining salts. The precipitates were dried in an oven at 40 °C overnight, followed by calcination at 650 °C (heating rate 1 °C/min) for 3 h. Fig. 2 shows the SEM micrographs of nanoparticles obtained by the experiment.

Figure 2 SEM images and EDX results of Mesoporous Bioactive Glasses produced by Micro-Emulsion Sol-Gel method.

Both silica and bioglass particles with pineal shape, and with the mean equivalent diameter of 150 nm were prepared during the experiment. The particles do not form agglomerates. The EDX results confirm that the glass nanoparticles contain 5-7 Atomic % Ca. The high resolution SEM micrographs revealed fine surface structure of the nanoparticles indicating their lamellar mesoporous structure. However, for unambiguous confirmation specific surface area measurements and TEM analysis are required.

Keywords: Drug delivery, Mesoporous Bioactive Glass, Nanoparticles

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